

IMPACT OF THERMAL LOADS ON THE DAMAGE ONSET OF FIBER REINFORCED PLASTICS

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ABSTRACT

In this study, quasi-static material tests on unidirectional and multi-angle glass fiber reinforced epoxy laminates at ambient temperatures from -213 K to 353 K (-60 °C to +80 °C) are performed. In addition, neat resin is investigated under tension and compression loads at different temperatures. The coefficient of thermal expansion is determined for neat resin and unidirectional reinforced specimens. The dependence of the resin's thermomechanical properties on the ambient temperature is shown. The point of damage onset at which first cracks appear within the matrix under quasi-static loading is investigated by means of optical grey scale analysis. The correlation between damage onset and effective matrix stress at different ambient temperatures is identified. An approach for the calculation of thermomechanical loads and the prediction of the damage onset by means of inverse calculations is presented. The impact of the strain blocking effect of the matrix is considered as well as residual thermal stresses due to curing and resin shrinkage.

1 INTRODUCTION

Fiber reinforced plastics (FRP) in aerospace or wind energy structures are often subjected to quasi-static and fatigue loading in a wide temperature range. A precise knowledge of the thermomechanical properties of the composite material as well as its constituents is essential for the computation of thermal stresses and strains. An improved computation of thermal loadings inside a composite structure will lead to a better understanding of thermal fatigue behavior of composite structures. Regarding the thermomechanical fatigue behavior of FRP, a correlation between matrix strength, residual stresses and damage initiation is proposed in the literature [1]. Therefore, a precise knowledge of the thermomechanical properties of FRP structures is important for the structural design with respect to quasi-static and fatigue behavior.

In this study, the combination of SE 1500 glass fibers and RIM 135 epoxy resin is investigated under thermomechanical loading and a model for the computation of matrix stresses and damage onset is proposed.

2 THEORY

The thermomechanical properties like stiffness, strength and coefficient of thermal expansion of FRP structures are directly depending on the temperature-dependent properties of its constituents. Particularly, the properties of the resin are substantially changing with temperature. Furthermore, the structural strength and the fatigue behavior of FRP structures is also influenced by thermally induced stresses. Residual stresses inside an unidirectional (UD) layer are the cause of the differing coefficients of thermal expansion of the fiber and matrix material and the shrinkage and moisture absorption of the matrix during curing [2]. However, interlaminar thermomechanical stresses may occur inside a multi-angle laminate due to the orthotropic thermal expansion behavior of each lamina.

2.1 Thermoelastic properties and strength of fiber and matrix material

Within the regarded temperature range of -213 K to 353 K, the elastic properties of most common fiber materials like carbon or glass fibers show no significant dependence on temperature. The tensile

strength of glass fibers decreases at temperatures above 420 K and for carbon fibers, no significant loss in strength and stiffness is observed up to 1300 K [3,4]. The properties of the neat fiber material are obtained by inverse calculation methods according to Krimmer and Zebdi [5,6]. However, the properties of epoxy resin matrix materials are highly temperature sensitive in this range. Provided that the material temperature is below the glass transition temperature of the resin T_g , a linear correlation of the tension strength $R_M^{(+)}$ and the compression strength $R_M^{(-)}$ of the resin versus the ratio of T/T_g is assumed in literature [7,8]. Furthermore, a linear correlation between the resin's elastic modulus E_M and temperature is shown in this paper, while its Poisson's ratio is supposed to be constant. Thus, the elastic constants of the neat resin can be expressed as a function of the ambient temperature T in Kelvin:

$$E_M(T) = c_1 - c_2 \cdot T \quad (1)$$

$$R_M(T) = c_3 - c_4 \cdot T \quad (2)$$

$$\nu(T) = \text{const.} \quad (3)$$

The constants c_1 , c_2 , c_3 and c_4 will be determined experimentally by tension and compression tests of the neat resin at different temperatures.

Below the glass transition temperature, the coefficient for thermal expansion of the neat resin α_M shows a linear dependency on the temperature. It is expressed in terms of

$$\alpha_M(T) = c_5 T + c_6. \quad (4)$$

The thermal expansion coefficient of an unidirectional layer in longitudinal direction α_L is calculated by a simple linear rule of mixture:

$$\alpha_L(T) = \frac{\alpha_M(T)E_M(1 - \varphi) + \alpha_{FL}E_{FL}\varphi}{E_M(1 - \varphi) + E_{FL}\varphi} \quad (5)$$

When α_L and the elastic moduli of fiber and matrix are known, by solving equation 5 for α_{FL} , the longitudinal thermal expansion coefficient of the fiber are calculated with:

$$\alpha_{FL}(T) = \frac{\alpha_L(T)(E_M \cdot (1 - \varphi) + E_{FL}\varphi) - \alpha_M E_M(1 - \varphi)}{E_{FL}\varphi} \quad (6)$$

The subscripts L and T indicate the fiber longitudinal and transverse direction of the lamina, respectively. The fiber volume fraction is given by φ . The transverse coefficient of thermal expansion of a layer are obtained by volumetric rule of mixture:

$$\alpha_T(T) = \varphi\alpha_{FL} + (1 - \varphi)\alpha_M(T) \quad (7)$$

2.2 Rules of mixture for the composite lamina regarding the strain-blocking effect of the matrix

For a layer-wise computation of thermomechanical loads in the composite materials, the elastic properties of each lamina are calculated with the rules of mixtures proposed by Krimmer [1,5]. These rules of mixture base upon a hexagonal packing of cylindrical fibers and consider a strain-blocking effect of the matrix. Therefore, Krimmer proposes an orthotropic in-situ behavior of the matrix. The elastic modulus of the lamina in transverse direction is given by

$$E_T = \frac{2E_M}{\sqrt{3}} \left[\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} - \sqrt{2\sqrt{3}\frac{\varphi}{\pi}} - \frac{\pi}{2\left(1 - \frac{E_M}{E_{FT}}\right)} + \frac{\frac{\pi}{2} + \arctan\left(\frac{\sqrt{2\sqrt{3}\frac{\varphi}{\pi}}\left(1 - \frac{E_M}{E_{FT}}\right)}{\sqrt{1 - 2\sqrt{3}\frac{\varphi}{\pi}}\left(1 - \frac{E_M}{E_{FT}}\right)^2}\right)}{\left(1 - \frac{E_M}{E_{FT}}\right)\sqrt{1 - 2\sqrt{3}\frac{\varphi}{\pi}}\left(1 - \frac{E_M}{E_{FT}}\right)^2} \right]. \quad (8)$$

Hence, the in-situ elastic modulus of the matrix is calculated in longitudinal direction by

$$E'_{ML} = \frac{E_T(1 - \nu'_{ML}) + E_M \nu'_{ML}}{\frac{E_T}{E_M}(1 - \nu'_{ML}) + \nu'_{ML} + 2\nu'^2_{ML} \left(1 - \frac{E_T}{E_M}\right)} \quad (9)$$

with

$$\nu'_{ML} = \left(1 - \frac{\nu_{FTL} E_M}{\nu_M E_{FT}}\right) \nu_M. \quad (10)$$

The transverse in-situ elastic modulus is given by

$$E'_{MT} = \frac{E_{FL} \left(\frac{E_T}{E_M}(1 - \nu'^2_{MT}) + \nu'^2_{MT}\right) \varphi + E_T(1 - \varphi)}{\frac{E_{FL}}{E_M} \left(\frac{E_T}{E_M}(1 - 3\nu'^2_{MT} - 2\nu'^3_{MT}) + 2(\nu'^2_{MT} + \nu'^3_{MT})\right) \varphi + \left(\frac{E_T}{E_M}(1 - \nu'^2_{MT}) + \nu'^2_{MT}\right) (1 - \varphi)} \quad (11)$$

with

$$\nu'_{MT} = \left(1 - \frac{(\nu_{FLT} + \nu_{FTT}) E_M}{\nu_M (E_{FL} + E_{FT})}\right) \nu_M. \quad (12)$$

The in-situ shear moduli of the resin result from

$$G'_{MLT} = \frac{E'_{MT} + E'_{ML}}{4(1 + \nu_M)} \quad (13)$$

$$G'_{MTT} = \frac{E'_{MT}}{2(1 + \nu'_{MTT})} \quad (14)$$

with

$$\nu'_{MTT} = \nu_M \frac{1 + \varphi \left(\frac{E_{FL}}{E_M}(1 + \nu'_{MT}) - 1\right)}{1 + \varphi \left(\frac{E_{FL}}{E_M} \left(1 + \nu'^2_{MT} \left(\frac{E_M}{E_T} - 1\right)\right) - 1\right)}. \quad (15)$$

Here, E_F and ν_F are the elastic modulus of the fiber material and its Poisson's ratio. The apostrophe indicates, that the strain blocking effect of the matrix is considered.

The longitudinal elastic modulus of the lamina under consideration of the strain-blocking effect of the matrix is given by a linear rule of mixture:

$$E'_1 = E'_L = E_{FL} \varphi + E'_{ML}(1 - \varphi) \quad (16)$$

The elastic modulus in transverse direction is calculated by

$$E'_2 = E'_3 = E'_T = \frac{2E'_{MT}}{\sqrt{3}} \left[\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} - \sqrt{2\sqrt{3} \frac{\varphi}{\pi}} - \frac{\pi}{2 \left(1 - \frac{E'_{MT}}{E_{FT}}\right)} + \frac{\frac{\pi}{2} + \arctan \left(\frac{\sqrt{2\sqrt{3} \frac{\varphi}{\pi}} \left(1 - \frac{E'_{MT}}{E_{FT}}\right)}{\sqrt{1 - 2\sqrt{3} \frac{\varphi}{\pi}} \left(1 - \frac{E'_{MT}}{E_{FT}}\right)^2} \right)}{\left(1 - \frac{E'_{MT}}{E_{FT}}\right) \sqrt{1 - 2\sqrt{3} \frac{\varphi}{\pi}} \left(1 - \frac{E'_{MT}}{E_{FT}}\right)^2} \right] \quad (17)$$

The shear moduli of the lamina are given by

$$G_{12} = G_{13} = G'_{LT} = \frac{2G'_{MLT}}{\sqrt{3}} \left[\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} - \sqrt{2\sqrt{3}\frac{\varphi}{\pi}} - \frac{\pi}{2\left(1 - \frac{G'_{MLT}}{G_{FLT}}\right)} + \frac{\frac{\pi}{2} + \arctan\left(\frac{\sqrt{2\sqrt{3}\frac{\varphi}{\pi}}\left(1 - \frac{G'_{MLT}}{G_{FLT}}\right)}{\sqrt{1 - 2\sqrt{3}\frac{\varphi}{\pi}}\left(1 - \frac{G'_{MLT}}{G_{FLT}}\right)^2}\right)}{\left(1 - \frac{G'_{MLT}}{G_{FLT}}\right)\sqrt{1 - 2\sqrt{3}\frac{\varphi}{\pi}}\left(1 - \frac{G'_{MLT}}{G_{FLT}}\right)^2}\right] \quad (18)$$

$$G_{23} = G'_{TT} = \frac{2G'_{MTT}}{\sqrt{3}} \left[\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} - \sqrt{2\sqrt{3}\frac{\varphi}{\pi}} - \frac{\pi}{2\left(1 - \frac{G'_{MTT}}{G_{FTT}}\right)} + \frac{\frac{\pi}{2} + \arctan\left(\frac{\sqrt{2\sqrt{3}\frac{\varphi}{\pi}}\left(1 - \frac{G'_{MTT}}{G_{FTT}}\right)}{\sqrt{1 - 2\sqrt{3}\frac{\varphi}{\pi}}\left(1 - \frac{G'_{MTT}}{G_{FTT}}\right)^2}\right)}{\left(1 - \frac{G'_{MTT}}{G_{FTT}}\right)\sqrt{1 - 2\sqrt{3}\frac{\varphi}{\pi}}\left(1 - \frac{G'_{MTT}}{G_{FTT}}\right)^2}\right] \quad (19)$$

The Poisson's ratios of the lamina are calculated by

$$\nu_{TL} = \varphi\nu_{FTL} + (1 - \varphi)\nu_M \quad (20)$$

$$\nu_{LT} = \nu_{TL} \frac{E_2}{E_1} \quad (21)$$

$$\nu_{TT} = \frac{E_2}{2G_{23}} - 1 \quad (22)$$

2.3 Calculation of residual thermal stresses

Residual thermal stresses can be divided into two categories:

Within a multi-layer laminate with different orientated layers, residual stresses occur because of the orthotropic thermal expansion behavior of each ply. They can be treated as external loads in the context of the Classical Laminate Theory [9]. Furthermore, due to the different coefficients of thermal expansion of the fiber and matrix material, thermal residual stresses exist within a lamina. For epoxy resin matrices, these residual stresses vanish almost completely at the temperature of curing [10]. The magnitude of the residual stresses in fiber parallel direction can be estimated by a simple linear elastic approach as a function of the difference ΔT between the operational and the curing temperature:

$$\sigma_{RM1} = E'_{ML}(\alpha_L - \alpha_M)\Delta T \quad (23)$$

Here, the subscript R indicates thermal residual stresses, α_M indicates the coefficient of thermal expansion of the neat resin and α_L the coefficient of thermal expansion of the lamina in longitudinal direction. At operational temperatures below the curing temperature as is usually the case, compressional residual stresses occur. For the residual stresses in transverse direction, a likewise correlation is proposed for a first estimation:

$$\sigma_{RM2} = \sigma_{RM3} = E'_{MT}(\alpha_F - \alpha_T)\Delta T \quad (24)$$

It should be noted that residual stresses in composites are subject to ongoing research. Since residual stresses appear during the curing process of the resin, they are influenced by many factors like thermal changes and phase changes (i.e. polymerization processes). Therefore, the proposed equations can only give an approximation of the actual residual stress distribution inside a lamina [11].

2.4 Damage criterion based on matrix effort

Krimmer [5] assumes, that matrix damage onset occurs, when the equivalent matrix stress inside the lamina exceeds the matrix strength, that means the damage criterion for the matrix is given by

$$\frac{\sigma_{Me}}{R_M} = 1 \quad (25)$$

The equivalent matrix stress σ_{Me} can be calculated with a strain energy approach according to Beltrami [12] in terms of

$$\sigma_{Me} = \sqrt{\sigma_{M1}^2 + \sigma_{M2}^2 + \sigma_{M3}^2 - 2\nu_M(\sigma_{M1}\sigma_{M2} + \sigma_{M2}\sigma_{M3} + \sigma_{M3}\sigma_{M1}) + 2(1 + \nu_M)(\tau_{M21}^2 + \tau_{M31}^2 + \tau_{M23}^2)} \quad (26)$$

The matrix stress components without consideration of residual stresses due to thermal, moisture or shrinkage loads can be calculated with the stresses from external loads σ_E and τ_E according to Krimmer [1,5] in connection with the proposed assumption for the residual stresses by:

$$\{\sigma_M\} = \begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_{M1} \\ \sigma_{M2} \\ \sigma_{M3} \\ \tau_{M23} \\ \tau_{M31} \\ \tau_{M21} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} \frac{\frac{\sigma_{1E} E'_{ML}}{E'_L} E'_{ML}}{\sigma_{2E}} \\ E'_T \left(\frac{\sqrt{2\sqrt{3}} \frac{\varphi}{\pi}}{E_{FT}} + \frac{1 - \sqrt{2\sqrt{3}} \frac{\varphi}{\pi}}{E'_{MT}} \right) \\ \frac{\sigma_{3E}}{E'_T \left(\frac{\sqrt{2\sqrt{3}} \frac{\varphi}{\pi}}{E_{FT}} + \frac{\sqrt{3} - \sqrt{2\sqrt{3}} \frac{\varphi}{\pi}}{E'_{MT}} \right)} \\ \frac{\tau_{23E}}{G'_{TT} \left(\frac{\sqrt{2\sqrt{3}} \frac{\varphi}{\pi}}{G_{FTT}} + \frac{1 - \sqrt{2\sqrt{3}} \frac{\varphi}{\pi}}{G'_{MTT}} \right)} \\ \frac{\tau_{31E}}{G'_{LT} \left(\frac{\sqrt{2\sqrt{3}} \frac{\varphi}{\pi}}{G_{FLT}} + \frac{\sqrt{3} - \sqrt{2\sqrt{3}} \frac{\varphi}{\pi}}{G'_{MLT}} \right)} \\ \frac{\tau_{21E}}{G'_{LT} \left(\frac{\sqrt{2\sqrt{3}} \frac{\varphi}{\pi}}{G_{FLT}} + \frac{1 - \sqrt{2\sqrt{3}} \frac{\varphi}{\pi}}{G'_{MLT}} \right)} \end{Bmatrix} + \begin{Bmatrix} E'_{ML}(\alpha_L - \alpha_M)\Delta T \\ E'_{MT}(\alpha_F - \alpha_T)\Delta T \\ E'_{MT}(\alpha_F - \alpha_T)\Delta T \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} \quad (27)$$

3 EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

All tests were performed with the Hexion RIM135 epoxy resin and Owens Corning Advantex SE 1500 glass fiber material with an areal weight of $300 \text{ g}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$ per ply. The resin is cured at room temperature for 48h and subsequently tempered at 353 K for 15 h.

For the determination of coefficients of thermal expansion, dilatometry tests were performed based on ISO 7991-1 using a Netzsch DIL402c Dilatometer. The fiber reinforced specimens and the neat resin specimens measure $25 \text{ mm} \times 4 \text{ mm} \times 4 \text{ mm}$ and have been cut out of a 4mm thick laminate plate with a water-cooled mill. Dilatometry was performed in a temperature range from 193 K to 373 K.

The tension tests of the neat resin and of the composite specimens were executed based on ISO 527, the compression tests of the neat resin were performed based on ISO 14126. Shear properties of the composite specimens were determined by $\pm 45^\circ$ tension tests based on ISO 14129. The tension and compression tests have been performed at a $\pm 20 \text{ kN}$ Zwick electromechanical tension/compression testing machine. The specimen extension was measured by strain gauges and by an optical ARAMIS 3D motion and deformation sensor. The temperature during the tests was regulated by a Brabender temperature chamber TEE52/LN2(80)X with an electrical heating and a liquid nitrogen cooling. The specimens for the neat resin tests were cut out of a casted plate using a water-cooled mill. For the composite specimens, plates have been produced using a modified Resin Transfer Moulding process. The specimens were cut out of the plates with a water-cooled precision saw.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To eliminate the influence of the variance in fiber volume fraction between the specimens, all results have been recalculated to a reference fiber volume fraction of $\varphi_{\text{ref}}=0.55$. Since there is only a small variance, a linear extrapolation approach is used.

4.1 Coefficients of thermal expansion

Figure 1 shows the thermal expansion $\Delta L/L_0$ versus the Temperature T , that was obtained by dilatometry measurements. Experiments were performed for the neat resin and transversal and longitudinal unidirectional glass fiber reinforced epoxy specimens. The corresponding coefficients of thermal expansion are received by derivation of the curves in Figure 1. They are presented in Figure 2.

Figure 1: Thermal expansion measurements of neat and glass fiber reinforced epoxy resin

Figure 2: Coefficients of thermal expansion of neat and glass fiber reinforced epoxy resin

Below the glass transition temperature, that has been determined to 358 K with thermomechanical analysis (TMA) measurements, the coefficient for thermal expansion of the neat resin α_M is calculated by equation 4 to

$$\alpha_M(T) = 9.29 \cdot 10^{-8} K^{-2} \cdot T + 8.18 \cdot 10^{-5} K^{-1}. \quad (26)$$

As well as the matrix, the fiber material has a temperature-dependent coefficient of thermal expansion. A significant temperature dependence of the thermal expansion behavior has been observed in silica glasses [13]. Therefore, a temperature-dependent thermal expansion of glass fibers seems likely. The evaluation of the dilatometer measurements and calculations of α_{LF} with equation 6 shows an approximately linear correlation between the longitudinal coefficient of thermal expansion of the glass fiber and temperature below T_g as shown in Figure 3. The dashed line shows the linear correlation.

Figure 3: Computed coefficient of thermal expansion of the neat glass fiber material

4.2 Matrix characterization

Tensile tests with neat epoxy specimens evidence a linear behavior of the elastic modulus of the resin with respect to the temperature as shown in Figure 4. Hence, the elastic modulus of the neat resin can be computed by:

$$E_M(T) = -13.0 \frac{\text{MPa}}{\text{K}} \cdot T + 6739.1 \text{ MPa} \quad (27)$$

The calculated linear approximation for the elastic modulus is shown by the dashed line.

Figure 4: Elastic modulus of the neat resin with respect to temperature

The compressive strength $R_M^{(-)}$ of the resin shows a linear behavior as a function of temperature, which is stated in Figure 5. For the tensile strength $R_M^{(+)}$, a linear correlation cannot be observed on the basis of tensile tests. Nevertheless, it is assumed, that the true material strength behaves in this way. This is shown by the dashed lines. Though, due to the very brittle behavior of the resin at low temperatures, premature failure occurs during standard ISO 527 tests at specimen imperfections. It is therefore proposed to investigate better methods for the determination of low-temperature tensile strength properties in the future. Tubular specimens could lead here to better results.

Figure 5: Tensile and compressive strength of the neat resin

The tensile and compressive strength related to the temperature of the neat resin can be expressed by

$$R_M^{(-)}(T) = -1.030 \frac{MPa}{K} \cdot T + 394.8 MPa \quad (28)$$

and

$$R_M^{(+)}(T) = -0.657 \frac{MPa}{K} \cdot T + 263.18 MPa. \quad (29)$$

4.3 Static properties of composite specimens and damage onset

Static tensile tests have been conducted with longitudinal (0°) and transversal (90°) unidirectional glass fiber reinforced specimens as well as with multidirectional ±45° glass fiber reinforced laminates at various temperatures. With inverse calculation methods [5,6], the glass fiber properties have been computed based on these test results at room temperature. For the material model, the fiber properties are supposed to be temperature independent, except for the coefficient of thermal expansion. The computed glass fiber material properties and the matrix properties are summarized in Table 1. The tensile strength of the glass fibers is determined by the technical data sheet of the manufacturer.

Material constant		Magnitude
$E_M(T)$	[MPa]	$-11.64 K^{-1} \cdot T + 6667.1$
ν_M	–	0.39
$R_M^{(+)}$	[MPa]	$-0.891 K^{-1} \cdot T + 341.7$
$R_M^{(-)}$	[MPa]	$-1.030 K^{-1} \cdot T + 394.8$
$\alpha_M(T)$	K^{-1}	$9.29 \cdot 10^{-8} K^{-1} \cdot T + 5.64 \cdot 10^{-5}$
E_F	[MPa]	82774
G_F	[MPa]	33999
ν_F	[MPa]	0,217
$R_F^{(+)}$	[MPa]	2400
$\alpha_F(T)$	K^{-1}	$1.41 \cdot 10^{-8} K^{-1} \cdot T + 5.33 \cdot 10^{-6}$

Table 1: Material model for the fiber and resin material

The results of the 0° unidirectional (UD) tests are given in Figure 6 for the elastic modulus and in Figure 7 for the tensile strength. The dashed lines show calculated results with the above-mentioned material model. While the calculations show a good correlation with the experiments for the elastic modulus, the experimentally determined tensile strength values are significantly lower than the computed values. Furthermore, an unexpected temperature-dependence is observed, because specimens should fail on account of fiber failure. Since the glass fiber strength is nearly temperature-independent in this range, it seems reasonable to assume that the actual dominating failure mechanism in this tests is matrix failure. Krimmer [5] observes the same phenomenon for 0° glass fiber reinforced epoxy specimens at room temperature. There are two possible explanation for that behavior:

(a) Krimmer [5] hypothesizes, that, due to the strain-blocking effect of the fibers, the matrix may have a local lower failure strain than the fiber material. Inter-fiber failure leads to a load rearrangement inside the lamina and, thus leads to early fiber failure. The level of matrix failure calculated with equation 25 is shown by the dotted line.

(b) A transverse compressive stress because of the clamping force is superposed with the longitudinal tensile loading of the experiment, which leads to inter-fiber failure.

Figure 6: Longitudinal elastic modulus of unidirectional reinforced specimens

Figure 7: Tensile strength of 0° UD specimens

The experimental determined elastic moduli and tensile strength values for the transverse reinforced UD specimens are given in Figure 8 and Figure 9. The calculated results are represented by the dashed line. While there is a good accordance of experiment and model for the elastic moduli, strength values are underestimated at elevated temperature levels, which will be subject to further research.

Figure 8: Elastic Modulus of 90° UD specimens

Figure 9: Tensile strength of 90° UD specimens

The calculated and experimental measured results of the elastic moduli for $\pm 45^\circ$ reinforced specimens are given in Figure 10. There is a good correlation between the analytical model and the experiments though the experimental measured elasticity at 340 K is apparently lower than the calculated value. This may be due to viscoelastic effects at elevated temperatures. The static strength is evaluated at a shear deformation of 5% according to DIN ISO 14129 (see Figure 11). Investigations with picture frame tests show, that this method overestimates the actual shear strength of the material due to the influence of adjacent layers [14]. Hence, a calculation with the introduced model proves to be difficult. However, the point of damage onset, where first matrix cracks appear, can be calculated and is shown by the dashed line. First tension tests at room temperature with greyscale analysis show a good correlation with the model.

Figure 10: Elastic Modulus from ±45° tension test

Figure 11: Strength and damage onset at ±45° tension test

5 CONCLUSION AND OUTLOOK

The introduced model for the calculation of static properties under elevated and lowered temperature conditions has shown a good accordance with experimental results for glass fiber reinforced epoxy resin in the temperature range from -213 K to 353 K. A linear coefficient of thermal expansion versus temperature has been validated experimentally and the correlation between elasticity, strength and temperature has been pointed out. In particular, the resin properties show a strong dependence on temperature. However, some fiber properties like the coefficient of thermal expansion are temperature dependent as well.

For further research, the application of a more sophisticated model for the calculation of thermal residual stresses is recommended. Experimental results for damage onset at different temperatures could lead to a better validation of these models. The proposed model for the stiffness and strength calculations should be validated with experimental results for different fiber-matrix constellations. Especially, orthotropic fiber materials such as carbon fibers will lead to further challenges.

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